

CLASSICA

Validating AI in classifying cancer in real-time surgery

D8.2 Bias

Document date: 28 April 2025

Document version: 1.2

Deliverable No: D8.2

Dissemination Level: Public

Full Name	Short Name	Beneficiary Number	Role
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE DUBLIN, NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, DUBLIN	UCD	1	Coordinator
INSTITUT DE RECHERCHE CONTRE LES CANCERS DE L'APPAREIL DIGESTIF	IRCAD	2	Beneficiary
STICHTING E.A.E.S	EAES	3	Beneficiary
EAES SUPPORT BV	S-EAES	3.1	AE
PINTAIL LTD	PT	4	Beneficiary
KOBENHAVNS UNIVERSITET	UCPH	5	Beneficiary
UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI TORINO	UNITO	6	Beneficiary
ZIEKENHUIS OOST-LIMBURG AUTONOME VERZORGINGSINSTELLING	ZOL	7	Beneficiary
ARCTUR RACUNALNISKI INZENIRING DOO	ARCTUR	8	Beneficiary
STICHTING AMSTERDAM UMC	VUMC	9	Beneficiary
KONVENT DER BARMHERZIGEN BRUDER GRAZ	BBGRAZ	11	Beneficiary
THE BOARD OF TRUSTEES OF THE UNIVERSITY OF ILLINOIS	UIUC	12	Beneficiary

Executive Summary

This report presents CLASSICA's 'ethics by design' approach, which addresses requirements and recommendations for avoiding bias in AI development. This work focuses on the requirements concerning bias in the EU AI Act, ethical guidelines developed by the High-Level Expert Group on AI, and WHO guidance on AI for health. The design choices mitigating biases in the CLASSICA project include prospective collection of data, multi-site studies, and randomised controlled trial, among other things. To ensure reliable and unbiased performance measurement, training and validation datasets are independent from testing datasets. Additionally, to detect biases in the system's performance, the performance can be evaluated in sex and age subgroups of patients. Subgroups for which the system exhibits poor performance, can be excluded from the future intended population.

The requirements of the AI Act concerning bias will apply from 2 August 2027 and unlike the ethical guidelines are legally-binding. Many of these AI Act's requirements have been addressed in the CLASSICA project by the abovementioned study design choices. To ensure that the AI Act's requirements related to bias are fully implemented, ARCTUR (technical partner) should 1) review their quality management system and include additional policies/methods for data management and bias detection and mitigation, as needed, and 2) make sure that the user interface of the system allows for correct interpretation of the system's scores and makes surgeons aware of potential automation bias (i.e., overreliance on the output of the system).

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
List of Figures	3
List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations	3
1 Introduction	4
2 Approach.....	6
3 Results.....	6
3.1 Analysis of the AI Act	6
3.2 ‘Ethics and governance of artificial intelligence for health: WHO guidance’	10
3.3 ‘Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI’ of High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence	11
4 Impact & Conclusion	12
5 References.....	13

List of Figures

Figure 1. Summary of biases in development and deployment of medical AI.

List of acronyms, definitions and abbreviations

AIA	AI Act
DoA	Description of Action
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HLEG	High Level Expert Group
MDR	Medical Device Regulation
RCT	Randomized Controlled Trial
WHO	World Health Organisation
QMS	Quality Management System

1 Introduction

Task 8.2 addresses the issue of bias and how the risk of bias has been and will be mitigated in the CLASSICA project. The following task description is included in the Description of Action (DoA):

‘Task 8.2 Bias (UCPH) M12-M36

This task will focus on the ethical concern of bias and will explore how to mitigate such risks in AI-assisted surgery. In particular, AI-driven technologies in surgery should be developed using an ‘ethics by design’ approach. We will analyze ethical guidelines, such as the WHO guidance on Ethics & Governance of Artificial Intelligence for Health and the Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI developed by the High-Level Expert Group set up by the European Commission. We will interpret this analysis specifically for CLASSICA, and will assess our system in the light of the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, in particular. We will use this to highlight possible causes of bias or ethical uncertainty, as well as avenues for avoiding these challenges. This will feed into the AI core work (WP1), and into data management throughout the project (WP2, WP4 in particular).’

This deliverable describes and draws on work conducted by UCD, both prior to the start of the project and currently within WP4 – ‘Clinical Validation’, specifically the robust design of three CLASSICA studies:

- ‘Study 1: generalisability and usability validation study, which aims to validate the results of a previous study conducted by UCD at different clinical sites;
- Study 2: biopsy validation, which aims to assess the use of the CLASSICA system for guiding endoscopic biopsy; and
- Study 3: resection validation study aiming to evaluate the use of the CLASSICA system for the assessment of tumour margins during Transanal Minimally Invasive Surgery.’ (D8.1)

This work presents the design choices in CLASSICA, which mitigate the risk of bias and address ethical guidelines and AI Act’s (AIA’s) requirements concerning bias. This report also highlights the AIA’s requirements concerning bias, which can be considered by ARCTUR within WP1 – ‘AI system refinement and support’ to ensure full compliance with the AIA’s provisions on bias.

Bias is one of the central ethical issues in medical AI. There are different types and sources of bias in AI systems [1,2] (Figure 1 below) and medical research. This task mainly focuses on dataset bias, arguably the most important type of bias in medical AI. Dataset bias occurs when datasets are skewed toward certain subgroups (e.g., defined by age or sex) or classes (e.g., healthy or cancerous tissue). This report also touches upon other types of bias, such as automation complacency bias (i.e., overreliance on an output of the system).

Potential Bias in the Various Stages of Data Collection and Model Development

Figure 1. Summary of biases in development and deployment of medical AI. This figure has been published in Gichoya et al. (2023) [1] under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).

2 Approach

UCPH's work in Task 8.2 has mainly focused on the EU AI Act and how it is relevant to CLASSICA. Notably, the AIA introduces extensive requirements for the quality of training, validation, testing, datasets, and addressing bias in the context of medical AI systems. The AIA was not mentioned in the description of Task 8.2 in DoA since, at the time of writing the project proposal, the final version of the AIA had not been yet published. Given that this regulation is now in force, applies to medical AI systems, and explicitly addresses bias, we have focussed on its relevant requirements. These, unlike ethical guidelines, are legally-binding. Additionally, many AIA's provisions draw on the ethical guidelines developed by the High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence. The results of the AIA's analysis are presented in a publication that is currently under review and publicly available as a preprint [3]. Below the AIA's requirements relevant to bias are discussed specifically in the context of CLASSICA.

Additionally, and as described in the DoA, this task involves an analysis of two guidelines on AI:

- High Level Expert Group's (HLEG's) 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI' (including the Assessment List for Trustworthy AI)
- 'Ethics and governance of artificial intelligence for health: WHO guidance'

This report discusses how the recommendations on bias in these documents have been or can be addressed in the CLASSICA project. It should be kept in mind, however, that the HLEG's guidelines do not focus on medical AI, but on AI systems in general. The HLEG explains that the 'Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) is intended for flexible use: organisations can draw on elements relevant to the particular AI system from this Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) or add elements to it as they see fit, taking into consideration the sector they operate in.' Hence, some of the recommendations may not be well-suited or easy to interpret and implement in the context of medical AI systems and studies, such as CLASSICA.

3 Results

3.1 Analysis of the AI Act

The AIA [4] entered into force on 1 August 2024. However, the obligations concerning high-risk systems (the risk classification system of the AIA is described in D8.1), to which CLASSICA belongs, apply from 2 August 2027 (Article 113(c), AIA). Additionally, the AIA introduced a 'grace period' for AI systems placed on the market or put into service before 2 August 2026. Providers of these systems do not have to meet the requirements of the AIA, unless the systems undergo significant changes after that date (Article 111(2), AIA). Given that it is likely that CLASSICA will be placed on the market after 2 August 2026, it is worth considering the AIA's requirements for the project, to facilitate future commercialisation of the system.

3.1.1 *Data governance and management practices*

Under the AIA, providers of AI systems (i.e., essentially, developers of the systems, Article 3(3)) are obliged to implement 'data governance and management practices' that concern training validation

and testing datasets (Article 10(2) AIA), as part of their quality management system (QMS). These practices should be tailored to the system's intended purpose and concern:

- ‘(a) the relevant design choices;
- (b) data collection processes and the origin of data, and in the case of personal data, the original purpose of the data collection;
- (c) relevant data-preparation processing operations, such as annotation, labelling, cleaning, updating, enrichment and aggregation;
- (d) the formulation of assumptions, in particular with respect to the information that the data are supposed to measure and represent;
- (e) an assessment of the availability, quantity and suitability of the data sets that are needed;
- (f) examination in view of possible biases that are likely to affect the health and safety of persons, have a negative impact on fundamental rights or lead to discrimination prohibited under Union law, especially where data outputs influence inputs for future operations;
- (g) appropriate measures to detect, prevent and mitigate possible biases identified according to point (f);
- (h) the identification of relevant data gaps or shortcomings that prevent compliance with this Regulation, and how those gaps and shortcomings can be addressed.’ (Article 10(2))

With regard to point f), given the medical purpose of CLASSICA, biases that may affect ‘the health and safety of persons’ are most relevant. To ensure full compliance with the above-mentioned requirements, ARCTUR’s software engineers, who analyse the data from clinical sites and develop the system, should review their QMS implemented according to the standard EN ISO 13485:2016/A11:2021 and add policies/methods for data management and bias detection and mitigation if they are not yet included. Many of the aforementioned requirements, however, have been addressed through the study-design choices, as described below.

3.1.2 Requirements for training, validation and testing data

The AIA also includes requirements for the quality of training, validation and testing data(sets). These datasets are defined as follows:

- Training data – ‘data used for training an AI system through fitting its learnable parameters’ (Article 3(29));
- Validation data – ‘data used for providing an evaluation of the trained AI system and for tuning its non-learnable parameters and its learning process in order, inter alia, to prevent underfitting or overfitting’ (Article 3(30));
- Validation dataset – ‘a separate data set or part of the training data set, either as a fixed or variable split’ (Article 3(31)); and
- Testing data – ‘data used for providing an independent evaluation of the AI system in order to confirm the expected performance of that system before its placing on the market or putting into service’ (Article 3(32)).

According to the AIA, training, validation and testing datasets must:

- be relevant (Article 10(3));

- be sufficiently representative (Article 10(3));
- be free of errors ‘to the best extent possible’ (Article 10(3));
- be ‘complete in view of the intended purpose’ (Article 10(3));
- ‘have the appropriate statistical properties, including, where applicable, as regards the persons or groups of persons in relation to whom the high-risk AI system is intended to be used’ (Article 10(3)); and
- reflect (Article 42) or ‘take into account, to the extent required by the intended purpose, the characteristics or elements that are particular to the specific geographical, contextual, behavioural or functional setting within which the high-risk AI system is intended to be used’ (Article 10(4)).

Many of these requirements can be considered ‘best practices’ in development and validation of medical AI and design of clinical studies, and, as such they have been taken into account in CLASSICA in the study design phase. CLASSICA studies use the ethics by design approach [5]. This means that the project is designed to mitigate risk of bias.

First, training, validation and testing data are collected prospectively at various locations in Europe (Dublin, Waterford, Turin, Amsterdam, Graz, Genk, and Athens) from patients for whom the system is intended. These are patients with rectal cancer or suspected rectal polyp/tumour undergoing surgical intervention or assessment. Sample size of the study cohorts has been determined in such a way to enable valid inferences/generalisability to the target population and account for potential study dropout [6]. This prospective multi-centre approach with clearly-defined inclusion/exclusion criteria and appropriate sample size [6] ensure that the collected data are relevant and representative of the intended patient group, that is, are expected to reflect the intended population in terms of age and sex distribution. Ethnicity or race of patients are not collected in the project due to legal and ethical issues as explained below (Section 3.2). However, data collection conducted in a few European locations ensures generalisability of the system’s performance to patients’ populations in regions where the studies were performed as well as any region of the world, where the intended patient’s characteristics are similar.

Second, participation rate in Study 1 is very high – the majority of the patients who were asked to participate in the study agreed. ‘Consent bias’, that is the impact of consent or lack thereof on the study cohort composition (e.g., in terms of age or comorbidities) in Study 1 is therefore minimal, if any. Participation rates in the studies will be reported in any resulting publications. If the participation rates in Studies 2 and 3 are lower, the impact of ‘consent bias’ on the study results will be considered.

Third, to ensure that the data are free of errors and of appropriate quality, clinical sites were instructed on how the videos should be taken, including the appropriate camera type and settings. This ensures that all classes analysed in the videos (i.e., healthy tissue and tumour) are represented and class imbalance bias is reduced. Additionally, the UCD team checks the quality of videos before they are sent to the technical partner. This ensures high-quality and consistency among videos from different clinical sites.

Fourth, the design of Study 3 (resection validation study that evaluates the CLASSICA system for tumour margins assessment during Transanal Minimally Invasive Surgery) is a randomised controlled trial (RCT) – a gold standard in clinical studies. RCT allows to avoid bias that overestimates the intervention effect thanks to the inclusion of a control group and allocation bias - through random

assignment of patients to the intervention and control groups. RCT design was not needed nor appropriate for Study 1 and 2. Study 1 is focused on data collection for training, validation and testing of the system. In Study 2 the sensitivity of CLASSICA-guided biopsy (where tissue classification is conducted by the AI system) will be compared to the sensitivity of standard colonoscopic biopsy. There is no risk of allocation bias or overestimation of intervention effect in these studies.

In addition to these study-design choices, there are also other measures to detect and mitigate bias, which will be used in the project, as appropriate. Training and validation datasets are independent from the testing dataset. Demographic characteristics, such as age, sex, country of origin, and relevant comorbidities, will be reported in any publications resulting from CLASSICA studies. In order to detect biases in the system's performance, the performance will be evaluated in sex, age and country of origin subgroups of patients, including the majority and minority groups (as mentioned in the WHO's recommendations below). Subgroups for which the system exhibits poor performance may be excluded from the future intended population of the system. Scientific literature provides other methods for bias detection and mitigation of biases in different stages of systems development that can be considered in the project, as appropriate [1,2].

3.1.2 User interaction biases

The AIA also addresses the risk of post-deployment biases. In Article 14(4) addressed to the developers of AI systems the regulation states that 'the high-risk AI system shall be provided to the deployer in such a way that natural persons to whom human oversight is assigned are enabled, as appropriate and proportionate:

- (a) to properly understand the relevant capacities and limitations of the high-risk AI system and be able to duly monitor its operation, including in view of detecting and addressing anomalies, dysfunctions and unexpected performance;
- (b) to remain aware of the possible tendency of automatically relying or over-relying on the output produced by a high-risk AI system (automation bias), in particular for high-risk AI systems used to provide information or recommendations for decisions to be taken by natural persons;
- (c) to correctly interpret the high-risk AI system's output, taking into account, for example, the interpretation tools and methods available;
- (d) to decide, in any particular situation, not to use the high-risk AI system or to otherwise disregard, override or reverse the output of the high-risk AI system;
- (e) to intervene in the operation of the high-risk AI system or interrupt the system through a 'stop' button or a similar procedure that allows the system to come to a halt in a safe state.'

Usability and user's perspective play a key role in the development of CLASSICA. The CLASSICA project addresses usability aspects, as required by the EU Medical Device Regulation, which overlap with requirements of the AIA. In particular, ARCTUR uses the standard EN/IEC 62366-1 'Medical devices — Part 1: Application of usability engineering to medical devices'. The system is tested in real-clinical settings that strictly reflect the context of future uses, that is, a surgery and real-time decision making. This allows detection and mitigation of any user interaction and automation biases (i.e., overreliance on the system's output) through appropriate design of the user interface. The interface of the CLASSICA system will be designed to clearly convey the meaning of the scores and avoid any

misinterpretation. Additionally, to make sure that the above-mentioned requirements of the AIA are addressed, ARCTUR should develop the user interface of the system in such a way that surgeons are aware of potential automation bias when using the system, to minimise the risk of overreliance on the system.

3.2 ‘Ethics and governance of artificial intelligence for health: WHO guidance’

WHO’s guideline was published in 2021, and features ‘the first consensus principles in this field’ identified and elaborated by twenty experts in collaboration with the WHO [7]. These principles include human autonomy, well-being, safety, public interest; AI’s transparency, explainability, and intelligibility; responsibility, accountability, inclusiveness and equity; and responsive and sustainable AI. The report also discusses laws and policies relevant to AI in healthcare; ethical challenges in the use of AI for healthcare; how to ensure that applications of AI in health are ethical; liability issues; and governance of AI for health.

Bias is addressed in the chapter ‘Ethical challenges to use of artificial intelligence for health care’, which discusses the implications of training medical AI systems on biased datasets. Biased datasets are datasets that are not representative of the population on which the AI system will be used. The report also includes an Annex for ‘Considerations for the Ethical Design, Deployment and Use of Artificial Intelligence Technologies for Health’. A list of considerations for developers includes a point focusing on biases (‘5. Address biases’). Specific considerations outlined under that point are listed below, with a discussion of how CLASSICA addresses these issues.

- *‘Determine how the study data were collected and how new study data will be collected, and look for any bias in the data according to the context.’*
- *‘Consider the majority and minority groups included in the data and whether any under-representation that results in bias can be mitigated.’*

These points are addressed above, in Section 3.1.

- *‘Examine the effects of ethnicity, age, race, gender and other traits, and ensure that AI technologies with biases do not have negative impacts on individuals and groups according to these different characteristics.’*

Race and ethnicity of patients and research participants are not routinely recorded in the EU due to their sensitivity and past misuses. Researchers have called for guidance from regulators ‘on the demographic characteristics of samples used to develop algorithms’ [8]. Currently there is no consensus nor standards that require collection of information about ethnicity or race in the absence of indications that these are relevant factors in a given study. The utility of these attributes is also limited by the fact that race and ethnicity have been defined differently across countries [9].

In the specific context of the CLASSICA project, there is no evidence that ethnicity or race affect the blood perfusion patterns in lesions, which are analysed by the CLASSICA system. Given the aforementioned concerns, as well as the GDPR’s data minimisation principle, which says that only data necessary to achieve a given (research) purpose can be collected, the collection of ethnicity or race

data in the CLASSICA project could have raised concerns of research ethics committees and regulatory bodies authorising clinical investigations. Consequently, race and ethnicity are not collected in the CLASSICA project.

Age and gender, as well as comorbidities, on the other hand, are collected from the patients. The system's performance in different age groups and genders will be reported.

- *'Prepare effectively and demonstrably for post-implementation surveillance of the application.'*

This requirement goes beyond the scope of the CLASSICA project. However, once placed on the market, the CLASSICA system will be subject to the extensive post-market surveillance requirements of the MDR and AIA.

3.3 'Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI' of High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence

The independent High-Level Expert Group on AI was established by the European Commission and mandated with the task of drafting deliverables to provide advice on AI strategy. Fifty-two experts representing industry, academia and civil society groups developed a report, which outlines conditions for trustworthy AI. These include 1) lawfulness, 2) adhering to ethical principles, and 3) robustness, 'both from a technical and social perspective' [10]. The HLEG guidelines discuss the two latter conditions as well as ethical principles and values; outline requirements that trustworthy AI should meet; and offer an assessment list for developers and other stakeholders in AI. The assessment list was revised based on stakeholders' feedback [11].

Bias is first mentioned in the HLEG guidelines in Section '2.2 Fundamental rights', in a paragraph titled 'Equality, non-discrimination and solidarity', which explains that 'equality entails that the system's operations cannot generate unfairly biased outputs.' A section on the ethical principle of fairness also discusses bias, while the list of requirements for trustworthy AI includes a point 'Avoidance of unfair bias.' The assessment list for trustworthy AI includes questions concerning bias, which may be considered by developers and users of AI systems. These are listed below:

- *Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?*
- *'Did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and/or subjects in the data?'*
 - o Did you test for specific target groups or problematic use cases?*
 - o Did you research and use publicly available technical tools that are state-of-the-art, to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?*
 - o Did you assess and put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the entire lifecycle of the AI system (e.g. biases due to possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets (lack of diversity, non-representativeness))?*
 - o Where relevant, did you consider diversity and representativeness of end-users and or subjects in the data?'*

As explained above (Sections 3.1 and 3.2), the data collection in CLASSICA is conducted in such a way as to ensure that the data are representative to avoid any unfair bias.

- *Did you put in place educational and awareness initiatives to help AI designers and AI developers be more aware of the possible bias they can inject in designing and developing the AI system?*

Task 8.2 and this report is such an initiative. In particular, this work provides guidance on the AIA's requirements concerning bias, which can be used by the software developers in the project.

- *Did you ensure a mechanism that allows for the flagging of issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?*
 - o *Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?*
 - o *Did you identify the subjects that could potentially be (in)directly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end-)users and/or subjects?*

Post-market surveillance mechanisms required by the MDR and AIA will include such mechanisms for the users of the system. There are no other subjects, besides healthcare professionals and patients that will be directly affected by the system.

- *Is your definition of fairness commonly used and implemented in any phase of the process of setting up the AI system?*
 - o *Did you consider other definitions of fairness before choosing this one?*
 - o *Did you consult with the impacted communities about the correct definition of fairness, i.e. representatives of elderly persons or persons with disabilities?*
 - o *Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?*
 - o *Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI system?*

There are different definitions of fairness as well as fairness methods, that is 'statistical approaches used to compare a performance metric or other statistical property across groups for whom an algorithm is used' [2,9]. There are also different approaches to minimise differences in AI system's performance between subgroups. Currently there is no consensus on the definition of fairness nor on the appropriateness of the fairness methods. Therefore, in line with the recent recommendations of the STANDING Together initiative focusing on bias in AI [9], currently CLASSICA does not assume any definition of fairness nor implement any specific fairness methods.

4 Impact & Conclusion

This report describes the requirements for bias mitigation included in the AIA and ethical guidelines and how they are addressed in CLASSICA. The CLASSICA project uses 'ethics by design' approach and, through robustly designed studies, minimises any risks of bias. The main strategies employed in the project include prospective study design, collection of data in different geographical regions of Europe, randomised clinical trial, and quality checks for videos. Furthermore, training, and validation datasets are independent from the testing datasets to ensure that performance tests are reliable. Demographic characteristics, such as age, sex, and country of origin will be reported in any publications resulting from CLASSICA studies. In order to detect biases in system's performance, the performance can be

evaluated in sex, age and country of origin subgroups of patients. Subgroups for which the system exhibits poor performance can be excluded from the future intended population.

This work also outlines measures that should be taken by ARCTUR in order to fully implement the AIA's requirements concerning bias – they can review their QMS and include additional policies and methods for bias detection and mitigation and make sure that the user interface of the system allows for correct interpretation of the system's scores and makes surgeons aware of potential automation bias (i.e., overreliance on the output of the system). UCPH team monitors the development of guidelines and standards for the AIA, which will contain details and technical solutions addressing the AIA's requirements.

This public deliverable can serve as a reference for researchers and developers of AI systems to mitigate biases in the development of medical AI. It presents legally-binding provisions of the AI Act for medical AI systems and discusses how they have been and will be addressed in the CLASSICA project. This can help developers of other medical AI systems in developing strategies addressing the requirements of the AI Act concerning bias.

5 References

- [1] Gichoya JW, Thomas K, Celi LA, et al. AI pitfalls and what not to do: mitigating bias in AI. *British Journal of Radiology*. 2023;96(1150).
- [2] Hasanzadeh F, Josephson CB, Waters G, et al. Bias recognition and mitigation strategies in artificial intelligence healthcare applications. *npj Digital Medicine*. 2025;8(1):154.
- [3] Niemiec E, Davis P, Hauglid M. Will the EU AI Act Help to Eliminate Dataset Bias in Medical AI? 2024. Located at: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5045561>
- [4] European Parliament and Council of the European Union. Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence and amending Regulations (EC) No 300/2008, (EU) No 167/2013, (EU) No 168/2013, (EU) 2018/858, (EU) 2018/1139 and (EU) 2019/2144 and Directives 2014/90/EU, (EU) 2016/797 and (EU) 2020/1828 (Artificial Intelligence Act). *Official Journal of the European Union*. 2024;2024/1689.
- [5] European Commission. *Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence*. 2021.
- [6] Moynihan A, Hardy N, Dalli J, et al. CLASSICA: Validating artificial intelligence in classifying cancer in real time during surgery. *Colorectal Disease*. 2023;25(12):2392-2402.
- [7] World Health Organization. *Ethics and governance of artificial intelligence for health: WHO guidance*. 2021.
- [8] Nguyen DL, Ren Y, Jones TM, et al. Patient Characteristics Impact Performance of AI Algorithm in Interpreting Negative Screening Digital Breast Tomosynthesis Studies. *Radiology*. 2024;311(2):e232286.
- [9] Alderman JE, Palmer J, Laws E, et al. Tackling algorithmic bias and promoting transparency in health datasets: the STANDING Together consensus recommendations. *The Lancet Digital Health*. 2025;7(1):e64-e88.
- [10] High Level Expert Group on AI. *Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI*. 2019.
- [11] High Level Expert Group on AI. *The assessment list for trustworthy AI (ALTAI) for self assessment*. 2020.